

“Red but not Daeng” – Some typical textiles of Tai Yo and their identity via traditional brocade in Vietnam

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Abstract: Tai Yo is one of the subgroups of the Tai ethnic minority in Vietnam, primarily residing in the provinces of Nghệ An and Thanh Hóa, located in the Northcentral region of the country. This study aims to introduce some typical textiles of Tai Yo’s brocade, categorizing them across various fields. Furthermore, we argue that while an approach based on brocade is necessary for identifying the identity of a Tai subgroup, it is not a decisive factor. In this case, although the color red is extensively used in Tai Yo traditional brocade, this does not align them with the Tai Daeng subgroup. Thus, this method alone is neither comprehensive nor entirely accurate.

Keywords: *Tai Yo, textiles, ethnic identity, Tai subgroups*

1. Introducing Tai Yo

1.1. On the ethnonym “Tai Yo” and people

According to the official classification of ethnic minorities in Vietnam promulgated in 1979, the *Thái*¹ people were identified as an independent ethnic group from other members of the same Kra-Dai language family such as the Lao, Lue, Tày, Nùng, etc. However, in reality, the Thái people in Vietnam are made up of many smaller local groups. These communities, beyond the similar features, also have enough differences to distinguish themselves from each other. Especially, that distinction is self-identified by them without any external classification imposed. This situation is identical to many Tai subgroups in Laos and Thailand.

As for the Tai Yo group, this is a large and representative subgroup of the Thái ethnic minority in Vietnam. Their traditional distribution area is located in the entire western part of Nghệ An province and a small part of the southwest of Thanh Hoá province. Yet, their residential area in these two provinces in the North Central region of Vietnam is not broken but is continuous. Indeed, their distribution area is only separated by “administrative boundaries” on the map.

¹ *Thái* is the original form from Vietnamese orthography, with acute accent *ó*. Don’t mistake it for *Thai* (without any diacritic) that refer to Thailand.

Historically, this continuous residential area of the Tai Yo people belongs to the area of three *phủ* or prefectures during the Nguyễn Dynasty:

1. *Châu Thường Xuân* (常春洲 - abbreviated as *Châu Thường*) was a part of Thọ Xuân Prefecture (壽春府). Today is in the range of Thường Xuân and Như Xuân districts of Thanh Hoá province.

2. *Phủ Quỳnh Châu* (葵洲府 - abbreviated as *Phủ Quỳnh*): this place name recorded since the Lê dynasty (15th century), in the annal named *History of Greater Vietnam* (大越史記全書) of Dai Viet kingdom. Nowadays, its range includes Quế Phong, Quỳnh Châu, Quỳnh Hợp districts and part of Nghĩa Đàn and Tân Kỳ districts of Nghệ An province.

3. *Phủ Tương Dương* (襄陽府 - abbreviated as *Phủ Tương*): this also appeared since the Lê dynasty with the name *Phủ Trà Lân* 茶麟府. Now it belongs to Tương Dương and Con Công districts of Nghệ An province.

In terms of ethnonym, apart from “Tai Yo” /taj⁵⁵ jo:^{53?}/ (in Vietnamese orthography, it is written as Tay Dọ or Thái Dọ; Lao transliteration: ໄທຍ໌ and Thailand: ไทญ้อ), this subgroup also has four other synonyms with the meanings they represent as follows:

Vietnamese orthography	English	IPA Tai Yo	Etymological transliteration in Lao & Thai script
Tay Mường	Tai Muang Tay Muong	/taj ⁵⁵ miəŋ ⁵⁵ /	ໄທເມືອງ (T) ໄທເມືອງ (L)
Tay Hàng Tổng	Tai Hang Tong	/taj ⁵⁵ ha:ŋ ⁵⁵ so:ŋ ²²¹ /	ໄທຫາງໂສ່ງ (T) ໄທຫາງໂສ່ງ (L)
Tay Xiêng	Tai Xieng	/taj ⁵⁵ siəŋ ⁵⁵ /	ໄທເຂິງ (T) ໄທຂຽງ (L)
Tay Pao	Tai Pao	/taj ⁵⁵ pa:w ⁵⁵ /	ໄທພາວ (T) ໄທພາວ (L)

- For *Tay Mường*, this name means “the people of the city”, implying that they (Tai Yo) are the main inhabitants, appearing before the surrounding subgroups of Tai and establishing their *meuang*/city here. Therefore, this term is used to notify the social status of the Tai Yo people, in the area where they are the majority and the pioneer to

arrive. And Tay Mường is an autonym. This phenomenon is the same with Lanna Tai people when they call themselves as *khon meuang*.

- For *Tay Hàng Tổng*, it means “the people who live in the *tổng* unit”. *Tổng* (總) “subdistrict” was an administrative unit in the previous feudal period, larger than a commune and smaller than a district. This endonym is used by the Tai Yo people to call each other, to distinguish who lives in the center of the *tổng* and who lives in more distant areas. However, this is not a true ethnonym but only a name indicating the geographical location between the Tai Yo people.

- For *Tay Xiêng*, its meaning: “the people who live in the central area”. *Chiang* or *xieng* in the Southwestern Tai languages means “the center”, which has the role of administratively managing dependent areas within the traditional *ban-meuang* institution of Tai people. This is an exonym of the Tai Yo people, used by the Tai Meuyay people in the Tương Dương district.

- Finally, for *Tay Pao* “the people who live along the Nam Pao river basin”. Nam Pao is the name that the Tai people here mention to one part of the Cả River which flows through the Tương Dương district of Nghệ An province. Nevertheless, my fieldwork shows that this term has never been used by the Tai Yo people here as an ethnonym to call themselves. Instead, the name Tay Pao is just a geographical indication and is used by all Tai subgroups here, the “Tay” in this name can be Tai Yo, Tai Meuyay or even Tai Nhai (aka Tai Thanh or Tai Daeng).

Among the above ethnic names, we believe that only the term “Tai Yo” is a real ethnonym (autonym) and could represent their identity. The above synonyms are only names that provide information about their geography and traditional social status. Also, using the term “Tai Yo” as an official identity is confirmed by their important folklore texts:

(1) *Lō Kǎm, Hún Vī, Mụn Kwāng. Mèn óng, mèn nāng Tǎi Yǎ*

/lɔː⁵⁵ kam⁵⁵ hun¹³ viː⁵⁵ mɪn²²¹ kwaːŋ⁵⁵ | mɛːn²²¹ ʔoːŋ¹³ mɛːn²²¹ naːŋ⁵⁵ taj⁵⁵ jɔː^{53?}/

“Three clans Lo Kam, Khun Vi, Muen Kwang. They are the noble class of Tai Yo”

[proverb]

(2) ...*Lō Ai lǒng nǎng tì*
Lō Ị lǒng nǎng mưōng
Lō Kǎm mèn óng mèn pā Tǎi Yǎ ...

/lɔː⁵⁵ ʔaːj^{33?} loːŋ⁵⁵ naŋ²²¹ tiː²²¹

lɔː⁵⁵ ʔiː²²¹ loːŋ⁵⁵ naŋ²²¹ miəŋ⁵⁵

lɔː⁵⁵ kam⁵⁵ mɛːn²²¹ ʔoːŋ¹³ mɛːn²²¹ naːŋ⁵⁵ taj⁵⁵ jɔː^{53?}/

“Lo Ai is down from the sky to reign the land. Lo I also follow him. Lo Kam is the noble clan of Tai Yo...”

[Extracted from *Lāi Kòp Kàw* “Telling the Tree of Pennants” in Tai Yo’s funeral]

(3) ...*Tǎw lùm fǎ hơ yu nhưn nhāw*

Bo kẹ Kéw hǎi Lāw, Tǎi Yǎ

Bo kẹ Kuôi, Mỏi, Hỏ, Hạng, Tǎi Thễnh...

/taw^{33?} lum²²¹ fa:^{53?} hơ:^{33?} ju:²²¹ jin⁵⁵ ja:w⁵⁵

bơ:^{33?} ke:²²¹ kε:w¹³ haj²²¹ la:w⁵⁵ taj⁵⁵ jơ:^{53?}

bơ:^{33?} ke:²²¹ kuəj^{33?} mơ:j^{53?} hơ:^{53?} ha:n²²¹ taj⁵⁵ t^hej⁵⁵/

“Those people gathered together under this Sky permanently. Not only Keo, Lao, Tai Yo. But also Cuối, Mỏi, Hỏ², Han Chinese, Kmhmu...”

[Extracted from *Hǎi Xông Phi* “Crying for Farewell the Dead” in Tai Yo’s funeral]

Evidence of the legitimacy of the term “Tai Yo” is also verified through some folk texts of the neighboring Tai subgroup – the Tai Nhai (with the synonym Tai Thanh, and in Laos Tai Daeng):

(4) *Yái kĩn hũa kọ, Yợ kĩn hũa hiêng*

/ja:j³⁵ kin⁴⁵³ hũa⁴⁵³ kơ:^{31?} | jơ:^{31?} kin⁴⁵³ hũa⁴⁵³ hĩa²¹/

“Tai Nhai eat the top of the palm *Livistona chinensis*, Tai Yo who eat the top of the palm *Livistona saribus*”

[proverb]

(5) ...*Xát pu pǎy mừa Lào*

Xát ǎo pǎy mừa Yợ...

/sa:t³⁵ pu:⁴⁴ paj⁴⁵³ mua²¹ la:w²¹

sa:t³⁵ ʔa:w⁴⁵³ paj⁴⁵³ mua²¹ jơ:^{31?}/

“The generation of our grandfathers returns to Laos. The generation of our uncles returned Tai Yo’s land”

[Extracted from a text used in the funeral]

² Cuối, Mỏi and Hỏ in this context are the subgroups and languages equivalently of Thỏ ethnic in the Vietnamese government’s official classification. All of them belong to the Vietic branch of the Austroasiatic language family.

Besides the evidence of the use of this autonomy in reality, the Tai Yo people as a local group of the Thái ethnic minority in Vietnam have also been studied from many different aspects. Some typical works can be mentioned such as:

- **Ethnological studies:** A. Louppe (1934); R. Robert (1941); Cẩm Trọng (1999); Hoàng Lương (2015); Lê Hải Đăng (2013); Vi Văn An (2017); Nguyễn Mạnh Tiến (2021)...etc.
- **Folklore studies:** Quán Vi Miên (2011), Sầm Văn Bình (2019); Trần Trí Dỗi & Vi Khăm Mun (2012); Phan Đăng Nhật & Vi Văn Kỳ (2005)...etc.
- **Linguistic and writing studies:** L. Finot (1917), M. Ferlus (1993, 1997, 2006, 2008...); Sầm Công Danh (2021, 2023)...etc.

1.2. The typical traditional attire of Tai Yo women

In terms of traditional costume, the Tai Yo also have differences between men and women. In this case, we will only mention the clothing of Tai Yo women because they inherently have more significant than men's, similar to many distinct cultures.

For the Tai Yo women, their clothing also has certain differences depending on the specific situation (normal or formal occasion). Despite this, we can still summarize the most core items of a Tai Yo women's outfit, which are:

1. **Blouse:** Historically, Tai Yo women's blouse was a short blouse called *xuơ tắw huợt* /siə^{33ʔ} taw^{53ʔ} hiət²¹/ “mid-waist short blouse”. This blouse, as its name suggests, is not longer than the waist. There are two types of mid-waist short blouses: the buttoned type (tied to cover the chest) and the buttonless type (the wearer just drape this blouse on their body). The buttoned type is common in Quỳnh Châu and Thường Xuân Prefectures, and the buttonless type is popular in Trương Dương Prefecture.

Figure 2: The buttonless type of mid-waist short blouse

On formal occasions, women's costumes are more elaborate. They often wear two types of long blouse: one is the long blouse in Tai Yo style (*xuơ nhắw* or *xuơ lôm*), and the other is five-part-dress blouse or “áo ngũ thân” (*xuơ bó bắt* in Tai Yo language) similar to the Kinh (Viet) people.

Figure 3: The long blouse in Tai Yo style. The left is an artifact, the right is Tai Yo women who were wearing it, circa 1920s.

2. **Waist belt:** *xái huọt* /sa:j¹³ hiət²¹/, or less commonly *xái éw* /sa:j¹³ ʔɛ:w¹³/. Frequently woven from silk to ensure durability. The color of the belt is red or light green. In Nghệ An, Tai Yo women often use the *xái huọt bọk* /sa:j¹³ hiət²¹ ɓɔ:k²¹/ “flowery waist belt” with both ends embroidered with many patterns.

Figure 4: The flowery waist belt in red by stick-lac

3. **Skirt:** or *xin* /sin³³/ of Tai Yo women is the tube skirt, worn as a pullover and the excess part is folded back. The tube skirt always has a portion of hem – *tín xin* /tin¹³ sin^{33?}/ woven or embroidered with various patterns; the body of tube skirt – *tō xin* /to:⁵⁵ sin^{33?}/ is usually a plain black background without any textiles. On the other side, there are also many types of Tai Yo women's tube skirt, depending on each type, the body of tube skirt is also decorated likewise. Inside the outer tube skirt is a layer of lining, called *xin hõi* /sin³³ hɔ:j^{53?}/ “sewed tube skirt”. And the waistband portion of tube skirt – *huó xin* /huə¹³ sin³³/ is a white fabric and long enough to cover the chest instead of a bra.

Figure 5: Two types of Tai Yo women's tube skirt. The left is a common tube skirt; the right is one for formal occasion - *xin bok* “flowery tube skirt”

4. **Head scarf:** or *khấn* /k^han¹³/ is used for the head. There are many different types of head scarf, from the unadorned or lightly decorated types (*khấn tá bông* /k^han¹³ ta:¹³ ɓo:ŋ^{33?}/ “eyespotted head scarf”; *khấn đằm đuôn* /k^han¹³ ɗam¹³ ɗuən^{33?}/ “totally black head scarf”) to the elaborately decorated ones (*khấn tãi* /k^han¹³ ta:j^{53?}/ “tailed head scarf”; *khấn chỡng* /k^han¹³ cə:ŋ⁵⁵/ “edged head scarf”).

Figure 6: A tailed head scarf or “*khấn tãi*”

5. Some other accessories such as hairpins, necklaces, bracelets, earrings... are often carved from silver and possibly gold.

Figure 7: The illustration of Tai Yo women's traditional costume. 1a: buttoned mid-waist short blouse, 1b: buttonless mid-waist short blouse, 2: flowery waist belt, 3a: common tube skirt, 3b: flowery tube skirt.

2. Some typical patterns in the brocade of Tai Yo

Similar to many other Tai, Tai Yo brocades are also decorated with many types of patterns. Within the range of this paper, we will mention some typical ones that are easily found in traditional items such as: blanket or quilt (*fā*), net (*xūt*), tube skirt (*xin*), head scarf (*khǎn*), cloth (*pha*)....

Basing on the meaning which these patterns reflect: both the physical world and the spiritual one, we divide them into three groups as follows:

2.1. The reflections of nature and ecology

Patterns in this genre represent living creatures such as animals and plants, such as:

Patterns	Tai Yo	Samples
Finger and toe of frog legs	<i>Tín khiết</i> /tin ¹³ k ^h iət ²¹ /	
Palm thorns	<i>Nám kǒ/Nám hiēng</i> /na:m ¹³ kɔ: ^{53ʔ} ~ hiəŋ ⁵⁵ /	

<p>Various elephants (real and mythical ones)</p>	<p><i>Chǎng ...</i> /ca:ŋ^{53?}/</p>	
<p>Fish</p>	<p><i>Pá</i> /pa:13/</p>	
<p>Primates</p>	<p><i>Līnh, Kǎng, ...</i> /liŋ⁵⁵, kaŋ¹³/</p>	
<p>Various horses (real and mythical ones)</p>	<p><i>Mǎ ...</i> /ma:53?/</p>	
<p>Various birds</p>	<p><i>Nòk...</i> /no:k²¹/</p>	
<p>Deers</p>	<p><i>Kwáng</i> /k^wa:ŋ¹³/</p>	

<p>Various plants</p>	<p><i>Kó</i> ... /kɔː¹³/ “tree” <i>Xên</i> ... /sen^{33ʔ}/ “climber” <i>Churō</i> ... /ciə⁵⁵/ “vine” <i>Bọk</i> ... /bɔːk²¹/ “flower”</p>	
<p>Insects</p>	<p><i>Mēnh</i> ... /mɛŋ⁵⁵/</p>	

2.2. The reflections of human living

These patterns reproduce familiar objects in people's daily life and work.

Patterns	Tai Yo	Samples
<p>The Sun or The Moon</p>	<p><i>Tá ngēn</i> /taː¹³ ŋɛn⁵⁵/ <i>Mạk bưón</i> /maːk²¹ biən¹³/</p>	
<p>Leaf stalks of coconut tree</p>	<p><i>Kan pǎw</i> /kaːn^{33ʔ} paːw^{53ʔ}/</p>	

Gong racks	<i>Hó kóng</i> /hɔː ¹³ kɔːŋ ¹³ /	

2.3. The reflections of sacred world

These patterns mainly represent mythical creatures, ferocious animals or totemic animals.

Patterns		Tai Yo	Samples
Various dragons & related reptiles	Dragons of Indic style	<i>Ngwòk Tǎi...</i> /ŋjə̀k ²¹ taj ⁵⁵ /	
	Dragons of Sinitic style	<i>Ngwòk Hən ...</i> /ŋjə̀k ²¹ ha:n ²¹ /	

	Snakes	<p><i>Ngū ...</i> <i>/ŋu:⁵⁵/</i></p>	
Tigers and Cats		<p><i>Xwó /siə¹³/</i> <i>Mēw /mɛ:w⁵⁵/</i></p>	

3. “Red but not DAENG”

Lexicologically, *daeng* in Tai languages means “red”. So why we give a title as “red but not red”? From the context of this paper, the title can be explained as:

1. *Red*: the primary and prominent color in the brocade of many Tai subgroups in Vietnam and Lao, including Tai Yo.
2. *Daeng*: beside the meaning red, it is a shorten way to point to a Tai subgroup known as Tai Daeng or Red Tai in Laos.

This title comes from an exploration which we discovered during our fieldwork on Tai Yo brocades: many of their brocades are being brought to Laos through trade routes, and there are also many personal collections here that own these products. Unfortunately, these products are often labeled as “Tai Daeng ethnic”, which is misleading to many interested people.

In fact, the use of red (mainly from sappan wood and stick-lac) as one of the prominent colors in traditional brocade items (especially head scarves, cloths of shaman, cloths for sacred rituals) is a *common practice* of the Tai subgroups in the vicinity between two provinces of Houaphan and Xiengkhouang (Laos) and the provinces of Hoà Bình, Điện Biên, Thanh Hoá and Nghệ An of Vietnam. These are the Tai subgroups such as Lao Noi, Tai Sam Nuea, Tai Khaw, Tai Daeng in the north; Tai Yo, Tai Nhai (aka Tai Thanh, Tai Daeng), Tai Phuan, Tai Meuyay, Tai Khang in the south. From the map, it can be seen that this is a large, long and continuous area.

Figure 8: The distribution of Tai subgroups using red as a prominent color

That can be reinforced through the evidence that: in this area, similar traditional brocade items can be found in adjacent places:

Cloth

Laos: Houaphan

Vietnam: Điện Biên (Vietnam)

Head scarf

Laos: Houaphan, Xiengkhouang

Vietnam: Nghệ An, Thanh Hoá...

Tube skirt

Laos: Houaphan, Borikhamxay

Vietnam: Nghệ An, Thanh Hoá, Điện Biên, Hoà Bình...

Blanket

Laos: Houaphan, Xiengkhouang, Borikhamxay

Vietnam: Nghệ An, Thanh Hoá, Điện Biên, Hoà Bình, Sơn La...

In addition, from the traditional brocade artifacts in the famous work “Lao-Tai textiles: The Textiles of Xam Nuea and Muang Phuan” by Patricia Cheesman (2004) and the earlier work by M. C. Howard & K. B. Howard (2002) titled “Textiles of the Daic Peoples of Vietnam”, it may be inferred that: the preference for using more red color is a **popular feature** of the Tai subgroups in the above mentioned area. However, this is more of a stylistic characteristic but not obligatory.

And of course, traditional brocade products can be found in many places in the picture ... not only of the Tai Daeng people of Laos who are usually recognized as using the red color more than others.

Figure 9: The "Using-more-red" area

Hence, the classification or labeling of any costume in personal collections, in museums or in showrooms really requires meticulous research. It is impossible to just rely on a few expressions of the costume's colors to label them as belonging to a certain ethnic group or subgroup.

Last but not least, for the case of "using-more-red area", we agree with the perspective of Patricia Cheesman (2015), she is really careful when saying that the classification of textiles, attires... needs to be based on factors beyond the surface of them such as historical political, geographical distribution: "...The style of Tai textiles and their dress codes were not a sign of ethnicity, but the result of socio-political interests that related directly to their communities and geographical locations".

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